

CESSDA Widening Activities 2018

Deliverable 5 – Gap Analysis of CESSDA Resources

Executive summary

After creating the CESSDA Resource Directory in the first part of the year, the project collected feedback from CESSDA partners – i.e. non-member Service Providers (SPs) – to provide a gap analysis of available resources within CESSDA and its SPs. The gap analysis was conducted during autumn with the partners.

Overall, the respondents indicated overwhelming support for the Resource Directory, confirming that the tool is useful for the building of a data archive service (DAS) and thus should be improved and kept up-to-date in the future. Most of the partners' questions and needs relate to the archiving activities and services of the DAS, followed by the technical infrastructure, staff capacity building, and the funding and advocating of the DAS. Partners' needs are expressed more specifically in each respective section of the document. The results show that the Resource Directory offers useful information and is an appreciated tool for the partners, which could be improved with more guidance and practical information for DAS in all development phases (i.e. conception, establishment and improvement), examples from working archives and training, as well as a more user-friendly interface.

Current resources are helpful in all categories, but more targeted resources should be developed. Among all the ideas suggested, we think that four resources are particularly crucial to develop:

- Data Archiving Expert Guide, where knowledge is systematised;

- Strategies and guidance for advocating for the needs of DAS for depositing primary data and using secondary data;
- Clear membership rules for CESSDA members;
- Help to implement locally and train staff to use the technical solution DataverseEU.

The various answers, comments, and ideas should be used further to adapt and develop future widening activities; activities from the CESSDA training, technical, tools and services, and trust working groups; and the INFRADEV proposal (GUIDE project).

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1. Introduction

The gap analysis is part of the broader task *Resource Directory for data service building and knowledge and capacity development* within the CESSDA project Widening Activities 2018¹. According to the task description, “the project will collect available feedback from non-member Service Providers (SPs) to provide a gap analysis” of CESSDA resources.

The aims of this task are to:

- find out if the existing resources that were listed in the Resource Directory address the partners’ needs;
- identify what kind of support is missing; and
- collect ideas to develop future resources and support.

1.1 CESSDA Service Providers involved

The institutions involved in this activity were the same as the ones involved in the development of the Resource Directory, namely: FORS (lead), ADP, CSDA, DANS, TARKI, and SND. Activities for the gap analysis primarily involved FORS, ADP, and TARKI, as CSDA, DANS, and SND were highly involved in the Resource Directory.

2 Process

2.1 Timeline

2017

December Kick-off meeting in Ljubljana

2018

January – August Development of the Resource Directory

September Development and sending of the survey “Your Opinion on the Resource Directory”

October Sending of reminders

Oct. – November Analysis of the answers

¹ For more information, see CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 - Deliverable 1: Resource Directory

November Presentation of the results at Belgrade meeting
 December Drafting of the deliverable

2019

January Diffusion of the deliverable to CESSDA working groups and to GUIDE’s work package and task leaders

All institutions contributed to the primary reflections and exchanges on how to proceed with this gap analysis, which questions to include and which collection method to use. In order to collect information on gaps in the resources and support offered by CESSDA and its members, we chose to send a questionnaire by email to our target groups. The two major target groups were CESSDA partners – i.e. non-member institutions or projects that are or could become a national data archive for the social sciences that were active in recent widening activities (WA 2018, CESSDA SaW) – and new CESSDA member SPs. We also contacted institutions in countries that are part of the European research area that currently have no active partners. In total, representative(s) of institutions in 28 countries were contacted (1 institution per country; table 1).

Table 1: Countries contacted by target groups

Active partners	New member SPs	Non-active partners
Albania	Belgium	Belarus
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Portugal	Israel
Bulgaria	Serbia	Malta
Croatia	Slovakia	Moldova
Cyprus		Russia
Estonia		Spain
Iceland		Turkey
Italy		
Kosovo		
Latvia		
Lithuania		
Luxembourg		
Macedonia (FYROM)		
Montenegro		
Poland		
Romania		
Ukraine		

FORS was responsible for elaborating the questionnaire. TARKI was in charge of conducting the survey, and ADP and FORS did the analysis of the results. The results were presented and discussed at the Belgrade meeting.

2.2 Survey “Your Opinion on the Resource Directory”

Based on the task’s aims, the questionnaire was designed to analyse the Resource Directory in terms of completeness, quality of the contents, and value for building a DAS. A first version of the Resource Directory (v1.1, September 2018), providing information and direct access to 160 resources, in excel format was sent together with the questionnaire on the 20th of September (see Appendix 1 and 2). The deadline for the answers was set for September 30th, but answers were accepted until the end of November to maximise the response rate. Also, two reminders were sent.

Given the numerous resources in the Directory, it was not possible for the respondents to review all of them in 10 days. In order to lower the burden for the respondents, in a first set of questions we asked them to report 3 problems or questions they have (or had) while building the archive and its services, and to assess if and how well the resources in the Directory help to answer these country-specific questions.² Since the development of the DAS is in a different stage in each country, not to mention the sharing culture and the support for building such an infrastructure, this strategy enabled search and questioning the Resource Directory with respect to a variety of demands and backgrounds.

While responding to this first set of questions, the respondents could become acquainted with the Resource Directory and its resources. In the second set of questions, they were asked if some topics or resources were missing. We also asked them to provide information on useful resources they know about and which were not reported in the Directory, and to provide ideas on additional resources that could be developed by CESSDA.³ Thus, the strategy of the questionnaire was to give the respondents the opportunity to comment on missing resources and support, as well as to propose new resources and ideas for support throughout the survey, for each question.

² In the excel sheet that contains the answers, these questions and their answers are mentioned as “Country-specific questions” Q1 to Q3.

³ These questions have been respectively coded as Q4-Missing topics, Q5-Other existing resources to be added, Q6-New/other resources from CESSDA and Q7-Other comments in the excel answer sheet.

In total, we received 17 completed surveys⁴ (response rate = 61%). All 4 new member SPs took part in the survey, 12 active partners and 1 non-active partner.

3 Results

In this section, we report on the results from the general to the specific topics in the survey, with both quantitative and qualitative analyses. The excel sheet with the answers will be shared with CESSDA MO and is available upon request to the person responsible for Widening Activities.

3.1 Do existing resources address the partners' needs?

Overall, the respondents appreciated the Resource Directory for the resources it provides and as a tool to look for and directly access the resources. The Resource Directory was helpful for answering 80% of the country-specific questions (Figure 1), either totally (31%) or partially (49%).

Figure 1: Are the resources in the Directory helpful for answering your questions/resolving your problems? (51 questions provided by 17 respondents)

This high rate shows on one hand that the Resource Directory is a useful tool for the target groups. This was further emphasized in the comments. Indeed, while we never asked directly for the respondents' opinions on the Resource Directory, 11 respondents (out of 17, so 65%) thanked us for a useful tool for the development of a

⁴ One completed survey, given by the country representative(s), corresponds to one institution and one country.

data archive and for providing in a single place direct access to pertinent resources for building a data archive:

*"It is **invaluable** for somebody who is starting a data archive."*

*"The resources currently provide – from our perspective – **everything necessary**."*

*"In general, I believe the resource directory is **extremely helpful** for data archivists or generally **for any institution** dealing with storing and disseminating data and metadata."*

*"It is a **great idea to have it all in one place!** Great job, thank you!"*

*"The idea about Resource Directory is excellent and **extremely useful**. We hope it **will be developed extensively**."*

On the other hand, the Resource Directory could be improved. Respondents found no answer for 20% of the country-specific questions (i.e. 10 out of 51). The analysis of the answers to the question: "... have you noticed a topic that is missing?" shows that all important topics are covered, but 10 respondents found that there are missing resources for certain topics. One respondent regrets that there are very few resources to guide the creation of the DAS from the very beginning.

One of the successes of the survey is that all 17 respondents, in different part of the questionnaire, gave ideas to develop new resources and to improve the Resource Directory as a tool.

3.2 Topics of interest in relation to the Resource Directory

To further analyse the results, we sorted all answers (i.e. from Q1 to Q7) using the same categories as for the Resource Directory. A maximum of two categories are attributed per answer. Answers without categories (e.g. because of no or irrelevant answers like thank-you note) are left out. In total, 75 answers (and 99 category tags) remained.

This allows us first to compare the questions and needs reported in the gap analysis to the resources available through the Resource Directory (version 1.1, Figure 2). We see that most questions relate to the core services and activities (35%) of the DAS, i.e. data acquisition (pre-ingest), curation (ingest), preservation and dissemination (access). Then, there seems to be three hot topics: technical infrastructure and software tools of the DAS (22%), staffing, management and internal structure and funding of the DAS (21%), and partner support and cooperation (19%). Few questions relate directly to communication (2%). There was no question on the definition of the organisation, i.e. mission statement, scope of the collection, beneficiaries, nor on the

evaluation and certification of the DAS. This shows that most partners already have at least a concept, but have more important needs (such as which services, staffing, and funding) before evaluating the quality of their services.

When we compare the reported questions and needs to the available resources (252), we see that the structure of the Resource Directory (v1.1) is quite different. Most resources are related to the services and activities of the DAS and “match” quantitatively the questions and needs reported in the gap analysis. This is not true for the other three hot topics, where available resources do not match topics raised. In the following sections, we will analyse more deeply the expressed needs and the ideas for future support.

Figure 2: Questions and needs reported in the gap analysis in relation to the available resources in the Resource Directory (v.1.1) sorted by category (in percentage)

3.3 Services & activities

3.3.1 Questions and needs

Most of the questions and expressed needs concentrated on the key activities of a data archive: data acquisition, curation, dissemination, and preservation. A second type of question focused on the legal aspects of a DAS's operations.

Data acquisition

The partners expressed difficulties in acquiring data. Reasons put forward are the lack of awareness, knowledge, and/or will (and sometimes interest) of the researchers, academic institutions, and funded research programs to archive and share the primary data. The lack of motivation among some potential data depositors is also due to low or zero level of financial resources provided for data management and cleaning before depositing the data in an archive. In this context, the questions are often how to encourage researchers to deposit their data in the DAS and what are the most efficient data acquisition procedures.

Data curation

Most questions focused on general data archiving standards, workflows, and processes: What are the best guidelines? What standards do the established data archives use? How to establish internal activities and organize the workflows? Most respondents needed best practice examples and models to ingest and curate survey/quantitative data on one hand, and qualitative data as well as other data types (historical, political data) on the other.

Data dissemination

Regarding data dissemination, a first question concerned the problem of convincing researchers to use secondary data. Second, more practical questions were asked about the dissemination package and citations: What is the best way to combine data and metadata into a single easy-to-use dissemination package for the end users? Users have to cite the DAS when using its content - should we offer a preferable citation format?

Data preservation

Fewer questions and needs focused on data preservation. Two institutions needed guidance and examples for preparing a preservation policy document providing a description of all stages of data preservation processes and a continuity of access plan (including a disaster/contingency plan) to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of data holdings.

Legal aspects of a DAS's operations

Various questions concerned the legal aspects of the DAS's operations, either generally or specifically. Respondents were interested in developing and updating (minimum) licenses and legal agreements binding data depositors and data users to the DAS. For this purpose they ask for examples. Respondents also wonder how to integrate the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) into their licence agreements. In relation to new changes under GDPR, there was a question on the legal and ethical considerations in data management. Moreover, a respondent asked for examples of consent forms for participants in different types of research. Another wanted to know how to deal with copyright issues and open data licencing. Finally, a specific question concerned data ownership: How to regulate work with existing "old" data if data ownership is unknown or not fixed?

The resources available via the Resource Directory were generally noted as completely helpful for questions on data curation and preservation, and partially helpful regarding data acquisition, dissemination and legal aspects (see Appendix 3).

3.3.2 Suggested resources

To help partners **to acquire primary data and to convince researchers to use secondary data**, the development of the following resources (documents, tools) was suggested by respondents:

- Guidelines to achieve a good overview of the various actors (i.e. researchers, institutions and research funding programs, etc.) that are likely to produce and/or reuse social science data, including actors such as national statistical offices, temporary research project teams.
- Guidelines/strategies to encourage researchers, institutions and research funding programs to share their data and use secondary data. One suggested strategy is to produce a document reporting public policies that have an impact on data management and sharing data in the social sciences. Also, data management is known to influence data sharing and reuse. However, users often have low expertise in data management practices, nor do they express satisfaction with their level of expertise, which raises the issue of providing a pool of relevant services (formal training).
- Best tools and practices to facilitate concretely the deposit of (online tools or others) and access to datasets.
- In order to facilitate the search for and use of secondary data, various tools were proposed such as, a tool that helps users find relevant questions/variables within poly-thematic surveys, or a tool or a tutorial that

helps to aggregate questions that are repeated in different polls but that differ slightly in wording.

In order to assist **data archiving** in general and data curation/ingest more specifically, partners suggest developing the following guidance and examples:

- Guidance on data archiving activities where knowledge is systematised and can be generally applied. A start could be to update the Archive Training Manual developed during SERSCIDA and available on the UKDA website. However, the guidance should contain more details. A way to do it could be to create a document similar to the Data Management Expert Guide, but for archiving activities and targeting (future) DAS staff.
- Examples of activities and workflows from working archives. Best practice examples can serve as a basic framework for developing a new service.
- List of software and tools used by the SPs to manage their tasks and workflows, with their evaluation (pros and cons). Also, a list of software and tools minimizing manual work from data depositors and archive staff, with their evaluation (pros and cons). See also section 3.4.2 for more suggestions on this matter.
- Technical documentation on specific steps of data ingest: i.e. anonymization, scripts for data pre-processing/cleaning, tools for workflow management, helpdesk, etc.

On **data preservation**, partners would like to have access to resources about disaster and contingency plans.

Concerning **legal aspects of the DAS**, partners are looking for:

- Examples of policies, deposit and user contracts from working archives.
- Recommendations for access/dissemination policy with unified set of norms.
- More recent resources on legal and ethical information especially in relation to the GDPR.
- Information on the management and archiving of data with unknown or non-fixed ownership.

3.4 Technical Infrastructure

3.4.1 Questions and needs

Questions about the technical infrastructure of a DAS can be grouped into 3 types.

First, most questions focus on the general **technical infrastructure of a functioning DAS and the software tools** needed and generally used for data

curation, preservation and dissemination, as well as for specific activities (like the implementation of DDI standards or the archiving of non-survey data).

A second set of questions targets **technical solutions without funding, IT expertise and lack of equipment**.

A third type of question was relative to the **CESSDA Data Catalogue** and how to connect the national catalogue to the CDC and the technical conditions for this.

The resources available via the Resource Directory were noted as partially helpful for the first and second types of question. No resources have been found for the questions concerning the CESSDA catalogue.

3.4.2 *Suggested resources*

To improve the current support relating to **technical infrastructure**, the resources to develop are:

- Guidance on best software tools and how to choose and implement them (with strictly expressed requirements and recommendations), as well as providing solutions for the implementation and use by non-IT staff and minimizing manual work for data depositors and the archive staff.
- Examples and description of the technical infrastructure and software tools used in established data archives to manage their tasks and workflows.
- Recommendations and guides on the infrastructure and software solutions for non-survey data archiving as well as software tools to handle with DDI.
- Add resources on the subject of metadata mappings/crosswalks (cf. conversion of DDI-encoded documents towards EAD-compliant ones).

Training and development of some specific tools are also mentioned:

- Training for IT staff and the general archive staff on the technical infrastructure and implementation and use of the software tools.
- Provide access in one place (create a “Software Directory”) to technical resources, software tools, web environments, catalogues and accompanying materials like CV’s, Dataverse, DDI schema, etc.
- Provide online and software infrastructure for service delivery and data management. There is a need for more effective collaboration tools and relevant data management software.
- Structured tools on organization of online spaces that support the volume of data generated and provide appropriate privacy and access controls.

Some resources target **CESSDA** directly:

- Provide a list with the exact CESSDA requirements on technical matters (and in general).
- Concrete instructions how to connect national catalogues (e.g. NESSTAR-based) to CESSDA Data Catalogue.

Finally, some partners mentioned existing resources that could be added in the next version of the Resource Directory: UKDA Qualidata documents, GESIS HISTAT system description, GESIS dara, GESIS thesauri, Datacite.

3.5 *Staffing, Management & Financing*

3.5.1 *Questions and needs*

In this category, most respondents asked questions concerned **funding**: How to get funding and secure it for the long-term? How to go from project-based funding to long-term funding (institutionalisation or creation of a unit)? How to overcome the lack of (national) funding? How to develop an archive on a voluntary basis, with no funding and no professional time allocated?

Moreover, questions about the **internal structure** of a DAS were asked, including the number of employees and the professional requirements for data curation, preservation and dissemination needed to build an efficient data archive. There were also questions on **management of outsourced services** like what are the important elements for the elaboration of service level agreements with third parties (e.g. for outsourcing technical infrastructure, IT team) and how to deal with outsourced services and solve conflicts.

Finally, needs for staff **capacity building** on the whole for the archiving process were expressed, as well as questions on how to overcome the lack of staff with capacities on establishing and maintaining a DAS or with IT expertise.

The resources available via the Resource Directory were noted as totally or partially helpful for staff and internal structure and as partially to not helpful for financing schemes.

3.5.2 *Suggested resources*

To help partners **to seek and advocate for financial support**, the development of the following documents were suggested:

- Overview and guidance through international funding agencies, programmes, frameworks.
- Guidance on the strategy and communication arguments to seek financial support of research and political institutions in the initial phase of establishment, as well as during operation of an archive, to become an institution (or a unit) rather than a project.
- Overview of the CESSDA SP funding schemes, i.e. who is the main funder of the data service (government, special research funds, private enterprises etc.), how much funding do they get and for how long (long-term vs short-term).

In order to **develop the capacity of the staff**, partners recommend active trainings:

- On-site presentations of a working archive and capacity building trainings for staff on key activities (OAIS model, data curation, preservation and access, archiving workflow and processes), as well as on the implementation and use of the technical infrastructure and software tools.
- Study visits to established data archives.
- Workshops and capacity building trainings on data archiving processes and on establishing and maintaining a DAS.
- Provide a list of certified trainers that could travel around Europe to give training to archive staff and to the academic community, for example when local (train the trainers) workshops and activities are organised.

3.6 Partner support & cooperation, communication & promotion

3.6.1 Questions and needs

Most expressed needs deal with **how to convince and seek support from different partners**, as their support is required to build and maintain a DAS. A first set of questions targets support from the Ministry and policymakers in order to receive the mandate and (long-term) funding for a DAS, sometimes in countries where the social sciences (and more generally academic world) are in crisis. Second, partners would like advice on how to make a convincing case to research institutions, academic leaders and researchers, to convince them of the importance of this service for the development of the social sciences.

Finally, the question on how to become **member of CESSDA** was asked. Partners are waiting for precise procedures and guidelines on minimum requirements.

Overall, the resources available via the Resource Directory were noted as partially helpful for CESSDA membership and advocating for partner support.

3.6.2 Suggested resources

To obtain the support and involvement of the governmental, funding and academic institutions and local academic community, partners suggest the development of the following strategies:

- Overview of best arguments for advocating the need to have a data archive for the ministries and academic community leaders (also in countries outside EU).
- A detailed description of the organizational and funding model of the existing archives (single institution, distributed structure, etc.) to use as examples for the ministries and funding partners.
- Inventory of policies and recommendations from national and international institutions on data sharing and reuse; shared with the different partners.
- Guidance on communication with the ministries and other partners, as well as communication materials.

Another idea mentioned to advocate the need for DAS and make the users and partners aware of it is to develop a cross-country mentorship and support in providing wide-scope educational programs on data usage for universities, governmental institutions, business (SEM, and corporate), libraries, NGOs, and mass-media.

Suggested resources concerning **CESSDA membership** are the following:

- Clear membership rules for CESSDA members which includes a detailed guidance with steps on how to become a full member of CESSDA, a list of the exact CESSDA requirements for SPs and members (governments) and what is expected from them, and a list of what CESSDA offers to its members (both governments and SPs).
- Mentoring during the process of joining CESSDA.

4 How to fill the gaps and offer a better support? Suggestions of closing-the-gaps activities

Plenty of ideas are suggested in the previous sections for developing new resources in the future that will better suit the partners' needs. We would like here to highlight some ideas that are, in our view, especially crucial and where CESSDA should work at first within its different projects and working groups:

- Guidance on data archiving activities, for example in the form of a comprehensive **Data Archiving Expert Guide** (useful for building new DAS and for training new staff in CESSDA SPs).
- **Strategies and guidance for advocating** for the DAS with ministries, funding and academic institutions to get support, formal approval and secured funding, as well as for advocating with the research community for using the DAS services (depositing primary data and using secondary data).
- **Clear membership rules** for CESSDA members (see section 3.6.2).
- A last important resource noted was to provide an online and software **infrastructure to archive and disseminate data**. The technical solution has been realised within CESSDA 2018 DataverseEU project. However, to answer this need, the technical solution should now be implemented locally and staff trained to use it.

It is also important to note that certain types of resources appeared systematically in the suggestions, giving us a hint of the types of resources they find useful, and which we should develop in the future:

- First, **guidance** as well as best practice, best arguments and best tools received overwhelming support (for example for deposit of primary data and use of secondary data, and for advocating and communicating with partners).
- Second, resources gathering **examples from working archives** together (on their activities and workflows, their access and dissemination policies and contracts, their technical infrastructure and software tools, their internal organisation and funding schemes) or inventorying possible tools, international funding programmes, and policies and recommendations on data sharing and reuse.
- Third, active support in the form of mentoring and especially **training** on-site, in workshops or study visits (for staff and IT capacity building and technical infrastructure).

5 Conclusion

Conducting this gap analysis has contributed to improving CESSDA knowledge on the usefulness of CESSDA resources and resources produced by CESSDA SPs for building a DAS and the need for specific support and resources, as well as to giving ideas for developing future resources that offer a better and more effectively targeted support.

In this sense, the results should be disseminated among other CESSDA working groups and SPs and used to adapt future activities, as well as to inform and develop the GUIDE (INFRADEV) proposal.

Appendix 1 – Contact e-mail sent on 20 September 2018

Dear CESSDA partners,

We are contacting you as representative of the local efforts for building or developing a national data archive service (DAS) in your country.

We are members of the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 team. At the Milan workshop in June, we presented the resource directory, one objective of 2018's activities. This resource directory has the aim of collecting and keeping in one place information about available CESSDA resources for data service building, as well as capacity development. The collected resources take different forms such as documents, support services, trainings and tools, which could help the CESSDA partners to build their DAS, develop their services and achieve CESSDA membership in the future. The resource directory will be available soon on the CESSDA website.

One other objective of 2018's activities is to conduct a gap analysis on the available resources in order to improve the next version of the research directory and develop future activities to close the gaps. We would kindly ask you to acquaint yourselves with the resource directory and the collected resources (you will find attached an excel version of the resource directory) and to answer our questions and insert your comments in the enclosed word document, **preferably by the 30th of September**. Once you have finished filling in the questionnaire, please send it by email to Peter ([email](#)).

The online version of the resource directory (offering a dynamic search with filtering options) and the results of the gap analysis will be presented and discussed during the Belgrade workshop in November.

Thanks in advance for your cooperation!

On behalf of the project team,
Christina Bornatici
Peter Hegedus

CESSDA

CESSDA's mission is to provide a distributed and sustainable research infrastructure and to facilitate teaching and learning in the social sciences. This enables the research community to conduct high-quality research in the social sciences. CESSDA aims to achieve

full European coverage by strengthening and widening the European infrastructure of social science data archives.

CESSDA has been on the ESFRI Roadmap since 2006, and in 2013 it has been pronounced an ESFRI Landmark institution, marking its successful transition from a project into an operational infrastructure. CESSDA has received its ERIC status in 2017. Presently 17 European countries are members of CESSDA ERIC, with several countries in the process of becoming a member.

More information on www.cessda.eu

CESSDA Widening Activities 2018

This project aims to build on recent developments and ensure the continuity of CESSDA widening efforts. CESSDA will maintain its network of CESSDA Partners, aspiring non-member service providers, from the CESSDA SaW project, and increase its visibility in non-member countries. The project: 1) organises two widening workshops in 2018; 2) provides a comprehensive guide into available CESSDA resources and support; and 3) maintains and further develops CESSDA strategic knowledge about existing non-member SPs and emerging national data archiving activities.

Appendix 2 – Survey “Your opinion on the Resource Directory”

Your opinion on the resource directory

Country:

Institution:

Person(s) involved in the evaluation:

Think of 3 questions raised or problems encountered while you were trying to build a data archive service (DAS) or to develop new services/features in your DAS. These could be precise or broad questions/problems encountered currently or previously.

- Please report these 3 questions/problems below.

Question 1: *Add your question here*

Question 2: *Add your question here*

Question 3: *Add your question here*

Now try to find answers to these 3 questions/problems in the resource directory (using the excel document attached to the e-mail). In the excel file, you can sort and filter the resources based on different categories.

- Are the resources in the directory helpful for answering your questions/resolving your problems?

Question 1:

- Yes, totally
- Yes, partially
- No

If partially or no, what kind of resources would you need?

Add your comment here

Question 2:

- Yes, totally
- Yes, partially
- No

If partially or no, what kind of resources would you need?

Add your comment here

Question 3:

- Yes, totally
- Yes, partially
- No

If partially or no, what kind of resources would you need?

Add your comment here

In general, on the resources available in the directory:

- Now that you have a better view of the available resources, have you noticed a topic that is missing?

Add your answer here

- Do you know of a useful resource that should be added to the directory?

Add your answer here

More generally:

- What additional resources (except financial) would you need that CESSDA and its members could offer?

Add your answer here

- Any other comments?

Add your comments here

Please send us this questionnaire back preferably by the 30th of September to Peter Hegedus ([email](#)).

Appendix 3 – Assessment of the usefulness of the available resources in answering the country specific questions

Table 2 displays the average assessment by main topics raised within each category. Questions Q1 to Q3 and their assessments are taken into account (i.e. 50 questions and assessments tagged 66 times). We see that in general current resources answer some questions and needs. Available resources on data curation and preservation are particularly useful for the partners. The only topic for which partners have not find resources in the Resource Directory is the CESSDA Data Catalogue. In all categories, there is room for improvement.

Table 2: Overall assessment of the available resources in the Directory, by sub-categories

Services & activities		Technical infrastructure	
Data acquisition (pre-ingest)		Technical infrastructure and software tools	
Data curation (ingest)		Technical solutions without funding and IT expertise	
Data dissemination (access)		CESSDA Data Catalogue	
Data preservation			
Legal aspects of a DAS's operations			
Staffing, management & financing		Partner support, cooperation & communication	
Financing schemes		Partner support	
Internal structure and outsourced services		CESSDA membership	
Capacity building (staff)			
	Totally helpful		Partially helpful
			No resources

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